

Participatory tools

DIA-LOG TOOL

INNOVATE TOGETHER DURING THE PROJECT PERIOD: CO-LEARNING FOR INNOVATION

How do we learn together?

Multi-actor projects are an opportunity to share skills, learn together and from each other, and increase our collective skills. This requires transferring and sharing. How do we ensure this transfer?

Participatory methods help take advantage of the diversity of skills brought together in the project and share these skills and experiences. Partners can learn from each other as the project progresses.

How to solve it

Sharing requires access to information, having related exchanges, and being well organised. It should be done regularly (see communicate transparently).

It works if everyone has access to information/products and can learn during the project. If some topics/skills are interesting for a large number of partners, you can plan collective training.

A dedicated space and time for the "inexperienced" can be created to practice and put into practice. You can encourage the

exchange and sharing of experiences in different ways:

- Mixed working groups,
- Create pairs between one experienced person and the other less experienced,
- Exchange of experiences in the form of interviews

Word of advice

Be careful not to gather the partners by skills and thus limit/make the exchanges and transfer difficult.

It is helpful to identify the levels of knowledge skills of each person at the beginning (individual surveys at the beginning can be replicated to see the evolution).

One example of a tool to facilitate this stage

Dia-log tool – Slowing down to listen and create together

Description of the tool

- **What:** to get different perspectives on a topic, explore a question further, find a common solution, synthesise a question with the group, and discuss it.

LIAISON Interactive guide to facilitating participatory projects

- **How long:** Between 50-60 minutes to 90 minutes. Depending on the question and the number of participants.
- **How many:** Small (8-10) to bigger groups (>20)
- **What you'll need:** circle of chairs, flip chart papers, markers

Steps:

- Dia-log is a process of developing creative thinking and critical thinking skills. It is very different from open discussion. Participants sit in a circle and the discussion develops from the centre. Questions are posed to the whole group. Periods of silence and slowing down the conversation are essential elements. By slowing down, participants can better perceive what conversation is developing within them.
- The facilitator clarifies the question and the framework (5 min). They hang the question on the wall as a poster and explain the context (e.g. how was the question asked? What do we want to achieve with the exchange?). They also explain the rules of the dia-log, the time frame, the role of the facilitator, the use of talking sticks, gong (start & end), etc.
- The facilitator carries out the dialogue (35 min). The talking stick is in the centre of the room. Those who want to speak, take it from the centre and replace it when they have finished speaking. Everyone expresses what they think about the question and what motivates their ideas. The participants do not respond to each other but rather express their points of view and feelings.
- The facilitator summarises (10 min). They gather the results on a flip chart (what were the common threads of the dia-log? What are the main lessons

learned?) Since a lot happens within the dialogue, it is a demanding task for the facilitator to summarise the results for the group.

Testimony of the use

Ruth Moser, Deputy Head of the Training and Advisory Group, Agridea, Switzerland

During the interview, Ruth Moser explained: "I really like this tool. I used it in a project where the momentum was waning. The collective was thinking of opening up to new members but didn't really know how to do it. Moreover, welcoming new people was scary for some of the members. The dia-log tool helped the group agree on a strategy, overcome their fears, and revitalise themselves.

I particularly like this tool because you have to slow down, and when you speak, you have had time for what you want to say to mature and even develop. It's very calming and constructive."

Tips

- Choose carefully a question that concerns everyone. For example, a common challenge without a solution etc.
- The facilitator refocuses expressions if necessary
- Suggest that participants do not take notes but listen carefully to what is said.

Another tool: Fishbowl (tool 55, [The MSP tool guide](#))

